

PAGUYUBAN REOGSARDULONARESWARI: A FORCE OF LOCAL CULTURE IN FOURTH INDUSTRIAL REVOLUTION ERA OF INDONESIA

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Abstract

This study discusses the potential of local culture Indonesia especially the performing arts reogponorogo as the power of the Indonesia tourism in the fourth industrial revolution era. Challenges facing the industrial revolution 4, Indonesia can develop and focus on potential industry owned in tourism. In his presence may also include cultural tourism where culture is as vital to reflect an identity and unifying the nation and amplifier as well. Like in particular the development of ReogPonorogo which has worldwide so that not only is struggling to catch up on technology trends. ReogPonorogo called SarduloNareswari. PaguyubanreogSarduloNareswari store unique compared with paguyubanreogponorogo. The uniqueness of the paguyubanreogSarduloNareswari were seen for the rest of its members is a woman. The existence and uniqueness of the SarduloNareswari when the reog further developed and dealt with seriously can be a potential cultural tourism international level where women as actors their motive. In addition, paguyubanreogSarduloNareswari is a form of expression of women in artistic activity. Writing method used is descriptive analysis with qualitative research method supported by literature study, observation and field study.

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1. Introduction

Indonesia is a country with ethnic, ethnic, cultural, religious diversity and characteristics and uniqueness in each region, one of which is the Ponorogo region. "BumiReog" is the name for the famous city of Ponorogo. Ponorogo is a small city located in the south of East Java, Indonesia which is directly adjacent to the City of Trenggalek in the east and Pacitan in the south, Magetan-Madiun Regency in the north and Wonogiri Regency in the west. Although a small city in East Java with an area of 1,371.78 km². Ponorogo has a global art namely ReogPonorogo. When entering the Ponorogo area, you will feel a strong Reog nuance. When entering the city of Ponorogo, will feel a strong feel of Reog. In the Welcome Gate, stand tall in light brown, there are two arches with two peacocks facing each other. Among the two peacocks there is the writing of Ponorogo. Under the two peacocks the lions lined up with figures depicting characters and a procession of reog in the form of Barongan, Klonosewandono, Bujangganong, Jaranan, Warok and Pengrawit.

Reog art that has shaped the image of Ponorogo city, for some people the name is not foreign and even has gone international. It is common knowledge that Reog is played by men, while women cannot participate. The majority in Ponorogo art, men hold a dominant role in their implementation. In the past, art practitioners were dominated by men because the view of women who went out and showed their bodies would be labeled as women was not good. The Reog show requires individuals to lift DadakMerak (Barongan) weighing over 50kg using teeth. The view of

the general public that those who can do this are men, because the image of women as weak creatures is inherent in the minds of the people

In fact, the view of weak women is denied by the Paguyuban Reog Sardulo Nareswari which is the only Reog community whose members are women. Paguyuban Reog Sardulo Nareswari is a community that consists mostly of housewives. They can divide their time between housework and regular exercise. Not only as a community, the women who joined the Paguyuban Reog Sardulo Nareswari also participated directly in the reog show.

The uniqueness of this Paguyuban Reog Sardulo Nareswari ought to be supported as one form of art preservation Reog Ponorogo. Sardulo Nareswari can be appointed from a different perspective. The existence of the Paguyuban Reog Sardulo Nareswari can be one of the tourism potentials for Indonesia in the fourth industrial revolution era. Now Indonesia is making various preparations to deal with the fourth industrial revolution era, including challenging economic problems, especially the issue of unemployment. Director of the Institute for Development of Economics and Finance (INDEF), Enny Sri Hartanti said, emerging country countries such as Indonesia do not need to pursue the trend of industrial revolution 4.0. According to Enny, Indonesia should focus on developing the industry in accordance with its potential, not too chasing ambitions in the digital technology sector. The sectors that need to be developed are tourism in addition to marine and fisheries, rubber production, and handicrafts. (Anadolu Agency News, 2018). Quoted from the website of Good News from Indonesia, disclosed Deputy institutional development of tourism areas of RI, Ahman Sya that tourism sector in the year 2017 occupy second place as the largest foreign exchange contributor. Therefore, the uniqueness of the Paguyuban Reog Sardulo Nareswari can be developed into an alternative cultural tourism. Women became an actor in the driving force of this cultural tourism. This is in line with the expectations of Indonesia's tourism sector to face the industrial revolution 4.0.

1.2 formulation of the problem

1. What is the dynamics of "Sardulo Nareswari Reog Circle of Friends"?
2. What privileges are carried out by the "Sardulo Reog Circle of Friends Nareswari"?
3. How can the potential be developed through the "Sardulo Nareswari Reog Circle of Friends" to face the 4.0 industrial revolution?

2. Research Methods

This research was conducted using qualitative ethnographic methods (Spradley 1997: 19). Ethnographic research is carried out by going directly to the community to examine a particular social reality of society. Where the information is not revealed in its entirety. The ethnographic research step is to establish informants, conduct interviews with informants, make ethnographic records and analyze ethnographic interviews. The data analysis was carried out through several stages including domain analysis (getting a general overview), to find out how the activities of the Sawoo village community, the relationship between men and women in Sawoo village and the social cultural of the Sawoo village community. this was obtained through general observations made on the Sawoo village community. After domain analysis is done, the next step is taxonomic analysis (in-depth observation), this is the development of data or information obtained from the previous stage, namely domain analysis. Where the data obtained was analyzed further through in-depth interviews with Sawoo villagers including members of the community, family and local residents. In-depth interviews are carried out as data reinforcers and as a comparison of previous data. Third is conventional analysis (looking for differences) after going through two previous stages, it is found differences that must be synchronized with the reality

that exists in the community. The final stage is the analysis of cultural themes (looking for red threads). Summing up the results of in-depth interview data in accordance with the data needed by researchers to be further processed.

3. Result and Discussion

3.1 The Dynamics of Paguyuban ReogSarduloNareswari and Women's Existence

Reog has become an artistry which is native for certain wider community, especially the people of Ponorogo, that in fact this city is naturally the place of origin of the establishment of reog. When ReogPonorogo is customarily performed by men, yet a new phenomenon emerges where women can be the main performers of ReogPonorogo. The existence of women in this custom was begun during 1978 after the adjustment of *jathilan* (a traditional dance) which was usually done by male dancer being replaced by the female one. The presence of women in this show triggers several reactions from both affirmative and negative sides in the society. The third Section Head of Department of Science and Education of Ponorogo issued an announcement about prohibiting women to appear as *kudakepang* dancers. The prohibition was stated in the decision letter of Department of Science and Education No. 644/II.04.19/J-78 dated July 1st, 1978 (AyuSutarto 2014: 4). The letter lamented that it was taboo for women to appear as dancers in reog. Nevertheless, this suppression could not be extended. Around 1985, male *jathilan* dancers were proceeded to be replaced by female dancers.

The substitution was occurred because the tradition in maintaining *gemblak* by *warok* had faded. In the past, *jathil* dancers were identical with *gemblak*. The maintenance of *gemblak* is a controversial side of *warok* in Ponorogo's custom. *Gemblak* is usually an attractive young man who is bespoken as *warok's* companion. This tradition arose as an effort to relieve the sexual urges without having a sexual relations with women. To have a relationship with women was believed to weaken the mysticism of *warok* himself. In the performance of ReogPonorogo, *gemblak* was dressed ladylike, and danced gracefully. *Gemblak* rose a controversy where it was said to be close to the practice of homosexuality, especially due to its flirtatious and limble dance movement which then made *jathilan* to be played by female dancers because it was considered to deviate the religious norms (Tri Suryanto, interview, June 4th, 2018). Momentarily, it can be said that the position of women as *jathilan* dancers is capable to shift the role of its male dancers that the existence of *jathil* male dancers is increasingly less appreciated and ultimately disappeared.

The existence of women in ReogPonorogo does not stop at *jathilan* figures. Until today, women still maintain their involvements in the show although discrimination often happens including the sexual harassment through *saweran*, compulsion for surrendering to the men through *Edreg* dance (*Jathil* dancers mannerly attract the dancers of *Barongan* and *Ganongan*) and the negative labelling for the female dancers of *Jathilan* for wearing too much makeup and unfitting costume.

In its development in 2015, the first female-based community of ReogPonorogo named *SarduloNareswari* was established. *SarduloNareswari* is the only one community which developed in Sawoo Village, Ponorogo. Socio-culturally, the majority of people who live in Sawoo Village, Sawoo District, Ponorogo, is Javanese who belongs to the Panaragan sub-ethnic culture. Javanese is the vernacular language used daily by people of this village. Like Javanese in general, who adhere to patriarchal culture, the authority and domination of men in domestic life and society is bold. Restrictions on women to do outdoor activities are a form of patriarchal culture in the Sawoo community. The biased gender construction in the Sawoo community is that women must be obedient, gentle and full of love which can be reflected in women's empowerment activities that focus more on domestic activities or feminine practices such as doing childcare and plant care.

3.2 The Values and Hidden Meanings Contained in the *Paguyuban Reog SarduloNareswari*.

The establishment of *SarduloNareswari* on November 4th, 2015 is one form of women's empowerment in Sawoo Village. Like the designation as the Women's Reog Community, all of its members are women. The selection of the name *SarduloNareswari* certainly has its own philosophy. *Sardulo* which means *Macan* (Tiger) and *Nareswari* which means women or angels (Tri HeniAstuti, interview, April 27th, 2018). Although in general, the criterion of reog dancers is man, but this community shows the feminine sides of reog without violating the standard.

Apart from its uniqueness as the only female reog community in Ponorogo, there is no doubt that there are pros and cons in its development. Initially, many parties opposed to the establishment of this community, especially those who acted in the name of religion. They forbade it because according to them, women were violating the nature of womanhood (Tri HeniAstuti, interview, April 28th, 2018). The prohibition has had a significant impact on the development of the *SarduloNareswari* as women's reog community.

In the early years of the *Paguyuban ReogSarduloNareswari*, it was opposed by many people which making it difficult to develop even it was ever been suspended for one year. Nevertheless, it did not reduce the spirit of the members this community to keep working. The members do not easily give up because they have a strong vision that loving and preserving ReogPonorogo has no bounds of gender; whether it is male or female. Efforts were undertaken by the chairman of the community along with the members so that its existence can be accepted by society. Various efforts had been made including looking for support from the government of Ponorogo. Because of the struggles that had been undergone, finally *SarduloNareswariReog* got the permission, and was recognized by the government as one of the artistry work of Ponorogo. Based on this recognition as well as support by members' positive activities, the people of Sawoo village finally began to accept the existence of the community.

The existence of *SarduloNareswari* began to reveal the gender equality. This community begin to alter the society's opinion that women are weak and unable to dance like man. Reog characters which was usually played by men were replaced and begun to be played by women. In general, it is impossible when the Reog's mask (*DadakMerak/Singo Barong*) which weighs up to 50kg played by women relying on the strength of the teeth as its cantilever. However, it can be done by Supreh as one of the player of *Singo Barong*. According to Supreh as a *Pembarong*, she can lift the Reog's mask by practicing the basics of the technique, and also is supported by her daily lawn mowing. The power that she has has no relation at all to the mystical things, as well as the other dancers. It proves that women also possess the power of masculinity akin to men.

Each show that was done by *SarduloNareswari* upholds the value of feminists, religious, and also other right aspects of the player. *SarduloNareswari* gives freedom to the fullest for its members including those who are moslem, and wears hijab, to keep wearing the hijab during the performance. The makeup being sets is different with makeup of Reog that played by the men, which tends to look creepy. The makeup used by the members of *SarduloNareswari* while staging using a proper makeup worn by women, which does not portray the scary impression. Feminist values is held strongly by the members of *SarduloNareswari*, despite of having to portray manlike characters, the dances performed by members of *SarduloNareswari* suits the standard or customary of female dancing, though its movements are firm, but it does not copy such gesture done by men.

SarduloNareswari become the pioneers to women's reog. *SarduloNareswari* is the first community that shows unique and interesting performance such as reog in a female version. In the artistic activity, gender is not a thing that should limit someone from crafting. This perception is held dearly by the members of the *SarduloNareswari*, as well as to bear the spirit in obtaining the identity that there should not be any limitation for women especially to dwell in art. Spirit, in terms of artistic activity, is the soul of the members who have been there since the community was firstly established.

SarduloNareswari has brought an impact for the emergence of women's existence. It shows a huge impact where women in the Sawoo village previously stood far from the spotlight, this time it begins to show their courage to perform in public. Their courage on showing the talent that they possess in public is supported by the existence of encouragement from within themselves and also from the others. The encouragement from within is proved by their desire to change the view of the society which assumes that the world of ReogPonorogo belongs to men. Their capabilities in terms of artistic skill is carried through *SarduloNareswari*. These women challenged themselves to appear in public to show their existence in artistic performance. The encouragement from the outside where the position of women in terms of art are equal with men, as well as encouragement from husband or family that supported those who appear in front of the public as the main lead of the arts of Reog (According to the Tri Astuti, interview, April 28, 2018). The performers of *Paguyuban Reog SarduloNareswari* themselves have been joining various performances both from or outside Ponorogo.

The impact that appears after the establishment of this for women in the Sawoo village is increasing their existence through a variety of activities that result in terms of art, economics and politics. In terms of the economics, women in Sawoo village, Ponorogo, gradually to work other than to be housewives such as trading in the market, opening a grocery store and also becoming self-employed worker with various businesses fields. This shows the level of independence is increasing after the founding of the *SarduloNareswari* where the Reog of Sawoo village has been received women's activity except work as a housewife. The existence of the *Paguyuban Reog SarduloNareswari* takes part to the emergence of women's groups in the new Sawoo village. Plus In case that women in the village who work as farmers in Sawoo village also formed the community of Farmer Srikandi of Sawoo's women. This community also markets their product in the Sawoo village. (According to the Tri Astuti, interview, April 28th, 2018)

The level of independence of the women in the Sawoo village, Ponorogo, itself can be examined from the large number of women who are working to help men. One example of an attempt at independence in economics after the emergence of *SarduloNareswari* Reog is the foundation of craft business called *Eblek* (Jaranan) which is a performance of trinkets of Reog itself. This craft is pioneered by the Sawoo's villagers, where its founder was a woman who was motivated by the existence of *SarduloNareswari*. She creates useful items to support *SarduloNareswari* when the team performs and also markets the results to her art craft outside the village as one of the strategies to introduce the craft. In addition to economic self-sufficiency, the women in the Sawoo village are also increasingly motivated by the existence of *Paguyuban Reog SarduloNareswari* where women can also work and produce something valuable. For example, in terms of politics, where there are few women in village incorporated in various gatherings of both official or unofficial activities, those women incorporated in the assembly, and dare to say their opinion in public.

3.3 Paguyuban Reog SarduloNareswarias a potential cultural tourism Indonesia in the Era of the industrial revolution 4.0

In facing the industrial revolution 4.0, all countries are trying to find their national potentials, both in terms of technology as well as tourism. One of the things that can be developed to face the challenge of industrial revolution 4.0 in Indonesia is tourism. One of the cultural tourism raised through art is ReogPonorogo which has been known worldwide. Based from its privileges contained in *Paguyuban Reog SarduloNareswari* which has been developed, it provides a new cultural tourism potential for Indonesia especially in Ponorogo, East Java. *Paguyuban Reog SarduloNareswari* is able to be developed into the new face or icon of ReogPonorogo, especially in the performed art that is usually played by men, then to preserve a unique side that is performed by women.

The concept of cultural tourism that could be developed by *Paguyuban Reog SarduloNareswari* is a package of village tour. In this case the woman was instrumental in the

economy of the village. Presentation of the concept of village tours are offered by the Sawoo village involves the entire community especially women artists who are members of the community and art studio. The concept was shown with the main event which is the appearance of the cultural procession on 1 Suro where SarduloNareswari became the main icon. This new cultural tourism destinations will be able to attract public attention because it has a unique side packed in an art show. The procession route featured in culture folder as follows:

Figure 1. Arak-Arakan Route “Ruwat Sawoo Village”

Figure 2. Cultural Map

The procession displays various art performances including the *Paguyuban Reog SarduloNareswari*, the Solahwetan dance studio and the Sawo Women's Srikandi Group. The procession route begins from Sawoo's village hall in collaboration with SolahWetan Dance Studio

to perform dances. Then the procession proceeds to the market and then headed to Petilasan Sunan Kumbul to conduct an adat procession as a form of respect for the ancestors. After that the route continues to the Sawoo sub-district office where at the final point displays a food bazaar from Srikandi Women's Group Sawoo and the main performance of the *Paguyuban Reog Sardulo Nareswari* as the main icon of the Sawoo Tourism village.

4. Conclusions

The art of Reog Ponorogo has experienced a long history. There are dynamics and contradictions contributing to the development of Reog Ponorogo. *Sardulo Nareswari* as the only female Reog Community in Ponorogo, where all of its members are women, emerged as a new Reog performance creations. The emergence of the *Paguyuban Reog Sardulo Nareswari* is increasingly showing the existence of women in the field of Reog. The existence of the *Sardulo Nareswari* reog community becomes an effective means, communicative as a form of entertainment (spectacle) as well as providing a good encouragement to women in freedom in all fields and equal rights in the public sphere. Positive values expressed through the *Sardulo Nareswari* community have an impact on women's lives in Sawoo Village. The impact arising from the existence of the *Paguyuban Reog Sardulo Nareswari*, among others, raised the independence of the Sawoo Village women as evidenced by women's participation in work other than as housewives. This raises a special exoticism to be studied so that it can form a concept of cultural tourism, so that this unique art can be widely known by the public not only in Indonesia but outside Indonesia. In addition, it is also in line with the industrial revolution 4.0 where cultural tourism can be used as an answer to these challenges, namely tourism as an economic reinforcement sector to face the industrial revolution 4.0.

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